

Yarns in “Tomb of Sand” (Reit Samadhi) by Geetanjali Shree

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Abstract: Women are special in every sense. They are specially crafted by Him with differences. Women in the “The Tomb of Sand” are equally different. There are three ladies symbolising different thoughts, beliefs, and life style. They symbolise an era, a love forgotten and unknown to many but alive in heart of Chandra Prabha Devi (Ma) and Anwar even after their separation after Partition. There was a time when they were in love and partition separated them but not the love they had for each other. Here is one lady who counters all the questions of Cops for crossing borders onlt to meet his love. Beti a free Modern woman living life on her own terms. And Bahu a mix of modernity and old culture and traditions. All portray a different world of their own. Beauty is that they being different are one.

Key words:- Women, Differences, Love ,partition ,Modern

Geetanjali Shree has combined many plots, characters, and stories to weave *Rait Samadhi*. She is the first Indian to win Booker Prize for her novel *Rait Samadhi* translated by Daisy Rockwell and turned *The Tomb of Sand*. She has touched human emotions of love, aspirations, and dejections. It has many characters who are life like and true in their essence. They represent Indian social system. Our world is full of people from different field but they occupy and play an important role in our life. This is one story where Eunuch, a tailor, gamlewala, milkman or every other and so have a significant role to play in every one’s life.

It is completely Indian in its theme, settings, relations, and emotions. It is a tale of Indian Women with emotions, pride, overconfidence, love, affection, and show-off for her and her family. There are mothers, soft, fragile, and strong who confide in their sons and daughters. There is daughter who is smart, independent and represents modern Indian free financially stabled Lady living life on her own terms. Every story has plots and characters. It is woven around Ma and Beti their emotions, relationships, highs and lows, understandings, love, care and compassion, fears, secrets, and openness. It has despair, agony, anguish, pain, and desperation and on the other hand, it has aspirations, desires, wishes, dreams, and expectations.

“Women are stories in themselves, full of stirrings and whisperings that float on the winds, that bend within each blade of grass”. (11)

It has women with different shades. It has affection and admiration and then it portrays despise and fear too. For every women world is different. They describe it as they want to see. It be new to one and the same may be old to other. “Things change with time for women.”(231) Life for women in earlier days was not what bahu and Beti are portrayed living. There must have been financial and social constraints. Though they are living in new world but, “the new age is tangled with the

old.”(232) Bahu, Bade’s wife, another woman in the novel is an Indian woman with self-appraisal and a self-proclaimed world where she controls everything even the emotions of her son. She pictures things in the frame she wants to see. She is a typical house wife who has webbed a world where she should be praised for all she did. She always frames statements with a taunt where arrow hits the target and none knows it. Her intentions were never so clear for her sister in law Beti. She was not jealous but vocal about the kind f life she used to live. That’s why she asks Bade to send Maa to Beti’s home for the sake of change. She described Beti’s life as, “nothing to worry about----she is free----she is alone-free from responsibilities-she is a freelancer.”(232)

Bade, Beti, Ma, and Bahu all were seen in different world. Beti changes her life to bring happiness to her mother’s life. Bahu, memsahib, the daughter-in-law was a wife to Bade and behaves as though she only manages everything at home. Beti, “daughters are made of wind and air”. Bahu was bahu busy with Bade and his world of Government jobs and affairs of transfer and celebrations. Bade works in the UP government which involves transfer so the walls and homes kept changing. The doors to Bade’s home know no constraints to the visitors. The word privacy is not even in a dictionary here. Shouting is a tradition, an ancient custom upheld by the eldest son. So was Bade, shouting at everyone whether he is to be blamed or questioned is unquestionable.

Bahu is being flattened by her other overseas son as he feels that she has been sacrificed on the family altar. Women of every race and creed meet this criterion. This type of son every mother has. Overseas son brought a cane which rested by Ma’s bedside as though it was a member of the house. When he was not keeping well bahu’s heart broke for her son. Ramdei took Bahu and their serious son to the tomb of Bahke Fakir, Pir Nabina 100 years old. Pir Nabina described his illness as he

cannot laugh, after this meeting he got promoted, and his company made him CEO of overseas offices, since then he became an overseas son. He brought a cane for Dadi. Bahu reminds everyone that she reminded his son to gift Dadi a cane stick.

Bahu is seen as a typical woman of every house just contrary to Beti. They do not nurture very emotional bonds. It was very artificial or superficial where emotion had no place. When she visited her house during Ma's stay, she praised the upper portion of the house as the one shown in the magazines or pictures. Bahu stated MA has turned her house into a home. She did not envy her lifestyle but Beti was the one whose life was different and free. There was a satire on the sister-in-law and bahu relationship, "sister-in-law does not desire the sort of life another lead, but they are pleased to see another deprived of the life they wish to lead."

We are made to believe in certain ideas from childhood. We are conditioned by beliefs, theories, and influences. Our thoughts frame us as someone like Hindu and Muslim, or Traditional and Modern. The conflict between the mind and life continues always. The same conflict is there between Anwar junior and Beti when they heard the story of Ma and Anwar. These theories govern our life and our thinking beyond it what is not acceptable to society in normal scenarios.

Ma, Chandra Prabha Devi, is "growing downwards" and her daughter is "growing upward". Ma is tuned in "a bundle shrinking even more from moment to moment". She has turned her back on the world and is stuck to the wall of her room. The relationship between Ma and her daughter was very unusual. She was more concerned for everything about Ma as "she had suffered so poor Amma and she lay there so sadly at Bade's house...it made her legs steadily weaker" (251). She takes everything in her hand about Amma for she plans to shift and postponing her relationship with KK. She told KK, "to let things settle first". As two swords cannot rest in the same sheath, mother and lover cannot inhabit the same skin....or sleep in the same bed either. (279).

Ma could never be at her daughter's house because of Bade's transferable job and now she managed to come to Beti's house because of another transfer. Indian society is still on non-acceptable terms with this set of relationships. Families do not agree. Relatives do not accept the unusual relationship. The same set of astonishment is felt by Beti during their visit to Khyber where Ma wished to meet Anwar her husband, whom she separated during partition. They nurture a humorous relationship as well. They talked about food, hair, dresses, and plants. They both laugh. Beti was happy for Ma. She allowed her to be in her skin and enjoy whatever she wanted to do, "Let her be happy,

do whatever she wants, here there are no rules as at babe's, none of the wife's demand, none of the foibles of the bureaucrats, wear as you won't speak what you wish, we are free, let's make a garden on the balcony"(260). They talked about the bloated belly, hair on the chin, mother and daughter nest in intimacy. Ma who has turned back to everything is having fun with her, she started walking, and they enjoyed tea on the balcony and watched films.

An Indian family is a complex web of relationships, too many of them mingled and intermingled even then so indifferently different to one other. Some relations are on the toss. Bahu on the same pretext desired freedom but always condemned the free life of Beti. Some unspoken grudges always survive and remain in the hearts if they are unaccepted. These relationships continue even after that as there is always a link or association that keeps them connected. The same Bade and Beti both are not on talking terms with each other still they maintain a distance so that their relationship may continue even after differences.

Indian society and family have a place for everyone may it be a faraway relative like padosi or one like Rosie Bua, a Tran's gender? Indian mythology has instances of transgender playing substantial roles in forming our traditions and culture and maintaining balance in society. Though they are not so accepted community at large. Because of Rosie Bua the life of Ma changed, she brought positive harmonious changes in life of Ma. Acceptance of Rosie Bua as a family member was not acceptable to Bahu but she was like a friend and the one with whom Ma opened her heart. When Bahu knew Rosie Bua became a regular visitor to Beti's house she surprisingly asked "The hijra?...she comes here too." She disapproved of her statement and firmly stated "There are no silly taboos at our place. And look how liberated MA feels. She doesn't lie lifeless here." Rosie Bua was a regular visitor to her place and the sense of her sis felt in every nook and corner of her house. Rosie Bua suggested home remedies for moles and skin tags and Ma was happy in her company.

Every society has a social set of norms and patterns where everyone is taken care of. By way of baksish, these people fended themselves. They visited everyone's house after festivals to collect grains, clothes, money, and other belongings for their survival. Society has been taking care of them in the form of baksish. Nowadays people are hesitant in accepting their way of life earlier this was not the system. Ma in the company of Rosie Bua adopted "a new posture for life" (313). Ma is now Bajji and beti is Baby. Rosie Bua got a nightie dress stitched by Raza tailor master so that Ma may be free in walking and "no fabric getting bunched between the legs" (318). Rosie Bua turned the

lifeless Ma into an unstoppable woman who started going downstairs with Rosie Bua and they would sit together on the step of “the medieval tomb in the green belt in the society” (320).

Another yarn in the novel is a plot where Rosie Bua is shown as a regular visitor. She is a Eunuch. Beti recalls Rosie Bua as the one who visited Ma when she was a child but Rosie Bua used to come from the backyard door, sit palms pressed away from others. She remembered “Sturdy Rosie Bua in a very colourful saree... or some type of sharara outfit”. Beti accepted everything in Ma’s life so that she may be back to life. Beti was improving Ma’s life in every way. The relationship between Ma and Beti was the centre. Every society has a social set of norms and patterns where everyone is taken care of. By way of baksish, these people fended themselves. They visited everyone’s house after festivals to collect grains, clothes, money, and other belongings for their survival. Society has been taking care of them in the form of baksish. Nowadays people are hesitant in accepting their way of life earlier this was not the system.

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Society is still not on cordial terms with old social taboos where people like Rosie Bua, childhood love, and live-in relations are acceptable. Ma who was adamant to meet Anwar her husband, Beti too became sceptical of the stories Ma drafted. She blamed Rosie Bua and her company Ma learned this nonsense. She disapproved of her mother’s first love for Anwar.

She was a prisoner when she was in Bade’s house. Rosie Bua gave her strength and liberated her soul and will. She lived what she had, a room, a wall, and her loneliness and lone thoughts. She confronted everyone and every question because she knew she was right. Now, she was adamant to meet Anwar, and when she met Ali Anwar senior a paralysed man who lay motionless, and a man with nope left. Ma and Anwar talked about the partition, Budha, and the changes the border bought into their life. She uttered “year they made you and me two separate countries. Anwar smiled”(694). They became the victims of partitions where many lost their life before starting. They also got lost in the same partition never to meet aging before this last time. Memories were fresh even after years of dismay and love was still fresh. They

shared their life with smiles and complained about the world for the borders and forgave each other in last for not coming to meet each other. Two lifeless cold lives smiled at each other in last to bid adieu. No one believed this can be the world. This was a world of beliefs, love, and emotions not to be judged.

Geetanjali Shree has beautifully drawn attention to lovers’ relations, living at will without getting married. This was the reason for contempt for Bade not talking to his sister. With KK she has developed a mutual relationship of understanding and respecting the space for each other. That’s why she doesn’t want to attend calls by KK after returning from Dar e Salam. KK and she had a life in their comfort zone. She remembers KK several times when she finds “bizarre drama”. No Maid, no bells, no unattended calls, no unannounced meetings or visits by people. Her life turns “bumper crop of bells” (280). She gets confused about doorbells or Ma’s phone bells. She is deceived by these bells and with every call she jumps to her skin. Still to all these, she accepts happily so that she may offer better comfort to Ma. Silence in her house is broken by Ma’s presence.

Conclusion : Yarn is normally a thread to be used for knitting. Here I have used the term yarn to knit relationship which are torn. They’re like but the warmth is missing. Geetanjali Shree the story teller has spined the yarns that keep the readers engaged and well knitted within the plots. All the character are knitted together well to give sense to the plot. Story moves round the characters and make readers connect to the emotions and at time take them in memory lane where they find same emotions attached to them or some co relations with the incidents.

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